

Rāga-s in Sabhārañjani – An Overview

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Abstract

The Indian Music tradition has been preserved and documented in the form of several lakṣaṇagrantha-s, source texts, translations of treatises and commentaries on texts that were written through the ages, which gives the historical evolution of various concepts pertaining to the tradition. They were written in various languages such as Dēvanāgarī, Tamil, Telugu, Kannada, Malayalam, Bengali, Marathi and so on. One such text written in the language Telugu, that serves as an important documentary work is “Sabhārañjani”. Sabhārañjani is a compilation of the concepts pertaining to Music and Dance where he explains about Carnatic and Hindustānī music, Rāga-s, Tāḷa-s, Instruments, Nāyikā-Nāyaka characteristics, Nāṭyābhinaya, characteristics of Vocalist and Dancer etc.,

Keywords: Ragas, Karnataka, Hindustani, Melakarta, Janya, Purusha ragas, stri ragas, raga-kala, Natyasastra, Sangitaratnakara.

1. Introduction

In the Indian Music tradition, various treatises have been written to document the concepts from time to time. Many treatises were named with the prefix “Saṅgīta”. The term Saṅgīta denotes Gīta, Vādyā, Nṛtya. Some texts were exclusively written on the South Indian and North Indian systems of music. The texts are available in various languages such as Devanagari, Telugu, Tamil, Kannada, Malayalam, Bengali, Marathi. There are numerous treatises on Music, Dance, Instruments, Tāḷa and many other aspects. These texts were written

in accordance with the regions and time period. The concepts pertaining to the different art forms were given equal prominence despite the region. Many authors have contributed to the development of Indian art forms in the way of documentation. ‘Sabhārañjani’ is one such text in which the author describes many of the music, dance and other aspects. This is authored by Velugōṭi Sarvagñya Kumāra Yācēndra Naiḍu Bahadūr. The general meaning of the word Sabhārañjani is that which is entertaining on the stage/or any place. Therefore, there is a possibility that the author would have named the book "Sabhārañjani" which gives information of art forms such as music and dance. This paper deals with the work Sabhārañjani with special reference to the Rāga-s.

2. Veṅkaṭagiri Rāja-s family Lineage

Allādi Jagannātha Śāstri, has written a book titled, “A Family History of Veṅkaṭagiri Rajas”, which gives the history and biographies of Veṅkaṭagiri Rāja-s. Accordingly, the first Rāja of the family is Bhētāla Nāiḍu. The antiquity of Veṅkaṭagiri Velugōṭi lineage is indeed unquestionable. The reign seems to have originated in 1195 A.D., and continued till 1917 A.D., as twenty-nine generations and they were titled with the position of Zamīndār-s. They ruled Veṅkaṭagiri in Nellore district and their capital was Velugōḍu in Kurnool district. They also extended their power in many places such as Amanagallu in Nallagonḍa tālūk, Pillamarri, Rācakonḍa, Dēvarakonḍa, North Mallūr to Veṅkaṭagiri, Perimiḍi, Madurāntakam, Velugōḍu. The Rājā-s had healthy relation with the rulers of Kākatīya, Vijayanagara, Bobbili, Jāṭprōle and so on. They adopted the surname Velugōṭi since they ruled Velugōḍu for a very long time. The royal court was adorned with great Telugu poets namely Kastūri Raṅgappa, Paṭṭābhirāmayya, Śataghanṭam, Gōpīnādhama Veṅkaṭakavi and so on also the Kings/Zamīndār-s have a great interest in literary works and some of them are great poets, musicologists and musicians. One

such Rājā, Velugōṭi Sarvagñya Kumāra Yācēndra Naiḍu Bahadūr of the same lineage (twenty-seventh generation) is the author of Sabhārañjani, the text taken for the study.

3. Author of the work Sabhārañjani

Velugōṭi Sarvagñya Kumāra Yācēndra Bhūpāla was born in 1831 A.D. to Baṅgāru Yācama Nāiḍū and Ammakamma. The author is known to be a patron of letters. He has also patronized Tārakabhūṣaṇam Venkaṭācāriar (guru of the Rāja) which is evident in his work, Śṛṅgārī Kalpavalli' in 1851 A.D. Velugōṭi Sarvagñya Kumāra Yācēndra Bhūpāla has written two philosophical books called 'Gītārthasāra saṅgrahamu' an exposition on Bhagavadgīta closely following the original text and 'Sārāmśa Pañcakamu'. He has also authored the book 'Sabhārañjani', which is a pamphlet on the art of music and dance. In addition to this, he has written a book that deals with philosophy called 'Manassākṣi'.

4. Sabhārañjani - An overview

The text Sabhārañjani is divided into eight chapters. They are as follows:

- The first chapter Nāyikā-Nāyaka prakaraṇa deals with the dance, dancers and their characteristics.
- The second chapter Rasa prakaraṇa deals with sthāyī bhēda-s for navarasa-s and other emotions.
- The third chapter Saṅgīta prakaraṇa deals exclusively with music and the characteristics of svāra-s, śruti, rāga-s, gamaka-s, different types of vīṇa and so on.
- The fourth chapter Tāḷa prakaraṇa deals with definition and characteristics of tāḷa, mārga-dēsī lakṣaṇa-s, yati, prastāra, sapta tāḷa-s, simhanandana tāḷa and other concepts.

- The fifth chapter Hindustānī rāga-tāla prakaraṇa deals with the names of saptasvara-s, tāla-s in dhrupad, traditional ways to sing hindusthānī, hindusthānī prabandha bhēda-s.
- The sixth chapter Nātyābhinaya prakaraṇa deals with aṅga bhēda-s such as śirō bhēda-s, dṛṣṭi bhēda-s, asamyuta hasta-s, samyuta hasta-s, manmadha pañca bāṇa prayōga sthala-s, brief discussion on pēriṇī, puṣpāñjali, śol for aḍavu-s.
- The seventh chapter Śabdavādyā prakaraṇa deals with the śol-s, names of the sounds.
- The eighth chapter Pāṇḍitya rahasya prakaraṇa deals with the eruditeness of vaiṇika (vīṇā artist), gāyaka(vocalist), instrumentalists, naṭṭuvanār's knowledge.

As mentioned above, the third chapter Saṅgīta prakaraṇamu deals with the various concepts and technical terms pertaining to music. The author discusses the various aspects such as śruti lakṣaṇa-s, trishāna lakṣaṇa-s, grāma bhēda-s, svāra-s, rudra vīṇā, acyutarāya vīṇā, mēḷakarta rāga prasthāra-s, śuddha madhyama mēḷakarta-s, prati madhyama mēḷakarta-s, kaṭapayādi saṅkhyā sūtram, śuddha vikṛta svāra-s, janya rāga-s, mūrccana prasthāra cakra, janya prasthāra cakra, aṅga-s, nyāsāmsāgraha-s, vādi samvādi vivādi anuvādi svāra-s, daśavidha gamaka-s and vīṇā daśa prāṇa-s.

The fifth chapter is devoted to the various concepts seen in the Hindustani system of music. The raga-s of Karnāṭaka and Hindustānī systems as discussed in Sabhārañjani will be dealt in the following sections.

5. Rāga-s in Sabhārañjani

Rāga is a melodic structure which plays a vital role in music, especially Indian music. Rāga-s are basically divided into two categories namely the Mēḷa rāga-s and Janya rāga-s. The term mēḷa was first coined by Śrī Vidyāraṇya svāmi in his text Saṅgītasāra, in which he

mentions 19 mēḷa rāga-s (janaka). “We first observe the Mēḷa-Janyarāga system of rāga classification in the Svaramēḷakalānidhi of Rāmāmātyā (1550A.D.). From another work of almost the same period, namely the Saṅgītasudhā attributed to Raghunātha Nāyaka, we gather information about an even earlier work, the Saṅgītasāra of Vidyāraṇyasvāmi, which also seems to have made use of the Mēḷa-Janyarāga system. However, it is only in the Rāgavibōdha of Sōmanātha that we find anything, which approaches a definition of the term mēḷa. Sōmanātha defines mēḷa as an ordered grouping of svāra-s or krama rūpa of seven svāra-s. In his own commentary to his treatise, named ‘vivēka’, he describes mēḷa as systematically arranging svāra-s for the purpose of grouping and classifying rāga-s.”¹ However, the other authors too used the term in their texts and have mentioned many mēḷakarta and janya rāga-s till day. The author of the Sabhāraṅjani has mentioned both Karṇāṭaka and Hindustānī rāga-s in two chapters.

5.1. Karṇāṭaka rāga-s

In this chapter, the author has mentioned various aspects such as Bharatamu. (Bharata śāstramu) that mainly talks about the ‘Tauryatrikamu’. The term ‘Tauryatrikamu’ refers to the triple confluence of Vocal music, Dance and Instrument music that constitute saṅgītam. (Nṛtyagītavādya) and also describes the significance of ‘Bhāvarāgatāḷa concept’. The term ‘Bharatamu’ in general also indicates the grouping of bhava-rāga-tāḷa.

The author discusses the 72 Mēḷa system as well as Kaṭapayādi saṅkhyā sūtram for mēḷa System. While naming the Śuddha svarathāna-s, instead of “Pañcama” he has mentioned the same as “Śuddha Pañcama”. He has discussed in detail, the naming of mēḷa-s with the help of Kaṭapayādi saṅkhyā sūtram. For example;

¹ Classification of Rāga-s under Mēḷa by N Ramanathan

• **Kaṭapayādi saṅkhyā sūtram:**

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
Ka	Kha	Ga	Gha	Ṇ	Ca	Cha	Ja	Jha	Ñ
Ṭa	Ṭha	Ḍa	Ḍha	Ṇa	Ta	Tha	Da	Dha	Na
Pa	Pha	Ba	Bha	Ma					
Ya	Ra	La	Va	Śa	Ṣa	Sa	Ha	Ḷa	Kṣa

౧ కనకాంగి = అనగా కాదినవ, యనుసంఖ్యవలన కకారముమొదలు యుకారమువరకు ౯ సంఖ్యయగుచున్నది కాబట్టి కాదినవలో, క, అనునక్షరము మొదటిది అట్టికకారము నాది యందు గలదిగాన ౧ టవమేళమని సంజ్ఞ - రెండవ యక్షరము లెక్కించగూడదనుటకు నిషేధార్థమునుదెలుపు సకారమును రెండవయక్షరముగా జేర్చినందున రెండవయక్షరమగు సకారమును లెక్కించ గూడదు.

• **Meaning:**

1 kanakāngi= the letter ‘Ka’ comes under one (1) and the letter ‘Na’ comes under zero (0) and the reverse of it is 01. So the rāga Kanakāngi is the first mēḷakarta and has given the svāra-s for the rest of the mēḷakarta-s.

3౭ సాలగము=ల 3 స ౭ కూడా 3౭ మేళము.
 దీనికీస్వరము
 శు-రి, శు-గాం, ప్రతిమధ్యమము, పం, శు-దై, శు-ని,
 3౮ జలార్ణవము=ల 3 జ ౮ కూడా 3౮ మేళము.
 3౯ ఝాలవరాళి=ల 3 ఝ ౯ కూడా 3౯ మే||

37 Sālagamu= the letter ‘La’ is 3 and the ‘Sa’ is 7. So it is 37th mēḷa and given the svarasthāna-s śu-ri, śu-gā, Pratimdyamamu, Pam, śu-dai, śu-ni,

38 Jalārṇavamamu= the letter ‘La’ is 3 and the letter ‘Ja’ is 8. So it is 38th mēḷa.

39 Jhālavārāḷi= the letter ‘La’ is 3 and the letter ‘Jha’ is 9. So it is 39th mēḷa.

The has designated the name of the 58th mēḷakarta rāga Hēmavati as ‘Hēmavantinī’ and 67th mēḷakarta rāga Sucaritra as ‘Sucāritrī’.

గీర హేమవంతిని = మ గీ హ ర కూడా గీర మే||

౬౭ సుచారిత్రి = చ ౬ స ౭ కూడా ౬౭ మే||

A mēḷakarta will get 484 Janya-s with bhēda in svarasthāna-s resulting in a total of 34,848 janya rāga-s for 72. This is referred to as ‘Mūrccana prastāram.

- Sampūrṇa ṣāḍava bhēda-s – 6 – Ārōhaṇa is sampūrṇa where it contains all the svāra-s and Avarōhaṇa contains one varjya svāra (missing svāra).
- Sampūrṇa auḍava bhēda-s – 15 – Ārōhaṇa is Sampūrṇa and Avarōhaṇa consists of two varjya svāra-s.
- Ṣāḍava sampūrṇa bhēda-s – 6 – Ārōhaṇa consists the varjya svāra and Avarōhaṇa is sampūrṇa.
- Auḍava sampūrṇa bhēda-s – 15 – Ārōhaṇa consists of two varjya svāra-s and Avarōhaṇa is sampūrṇa.
- Ṣāḍava ṣāḍava bhēda-s – 36 – Ārōhaṇa and Avarōhaṇa consists of one varjya svāra.
- Ṣāḍava auḍava bhēda-s – 60 – Ārōhaṇa consists of one varjya svāra and Avarōhaṇa consists of two varjya svāra-s.
- Auḍava ṣāḍava bhēda-s – 60 – Ārōhaṇa consists of two varjya svāra-s and Avarōhaṇa consists of one varjya svāra.
- Auḍava auḍava bhēda-s – 225 – Ārōhaṇa and Avarōhaṇa consists of two varjya svāra-s.

For example, the janya bhēda-s in Mēḷakarta Kanakāṅgi are 484 rāga-s, and the janya bhēda-s for 72 Mēḷakart-s give rise to 34848 rāga-s.

However, several of the jañya-s are not in use today and some of them may not have the names also.

He also talks about the rāga classification such as

- Rāgāṅga rāga-s: Sampūrṇa mēḷakarta rāgā-s.
- Upāṅga rāga-s: Janyā-s acquired from the mēḷā-s with auḍava, śāḍava and varjya svarā-s.
- Kriyāṅga rāga-s: Rāga-s that evolve from vakra prayōga, used extensively in hindustānī music.
- Dēśāṅga rāga-s: Rāgā-s that emerge by the collaboration of two rāgā-s.

It is to be noted that the author has used the term Dēśāṅga but not Bhāṣāṅga. The term Dēśāṅga may indicate the usage according to each region.

1.7 Chapter on Hindustānī rāga-s

In the preface of the text, the author has mentioned that this particular chapter was written based on the interactions the author had with the Hindustānī musicians in his court. The rāga-s that are sung in Hindustāna dēśa (North India) are known as Hindustānī rāga-s. Similar to Karṇāṭaka rāga-s, Hindustānī rāga-s are also huge in number. The Hindustānī rāga-s are broadly divided into ‘Puruṣa rāga-s and Strī rāga-s’, and the rest are to be known as ‘Janya rāga-s’. Hindustānī rāga-s follow the rāga-kāla (time that is appropriate to sing the particular rāga).

There are six puruṣa rāga-s, and each has six strī rāga-s. As a result, there are a total of six puruṣa rāga-s and thirty-six strī rāga-s.

1.7.1 Puruṣa rāga-s

- Mēgh
- Siri
- Dīpak
- Hindōl
- Mālkauns
- Bhairo

The rest 36 are the rāgiṇi-s(wives). However, the author has not mentioned the names of the rāgiṇi-s. The raga-s that acquire from rāga-s and rāgiṇi-s are the jañya rāga-s.

According to Saṅgītaratnākara of Śāraṅgadēva and the few other treaties, rāga-rāgiṇi-s arise due to the differences between grāma-mūrccana, nyāsāmśa, graha svara-s and vakra svara-s as well as integration of different rāga-s (rāgamēḷana).

1.7.2 Rāga-kāla and the Rāga-s:

The author has listed the rāga-s according to the rāga-kāla, where he mentions the rāga-s that are to be sung according to the time and weather.

- **Pūrvanah (Dawn):**

Bilāval	Alayyābilāval	Alayyā
Gouḍbilāval	Sudbilāval	Naṭbilāval
Suvābilāval	Sugaraibilāval	Suvā
Sugarai	Kōkabbilāval	Naṭnārāyan
Suraṭbilāval	Barārā	

• **Madhyāhna (Morning):**

Barārātōḍi	Tōḍi	Hasātōḍi
Dēstōḍi	Sindhutōḍi	Sāvarī
Asāvarī	Barahans	Barahanssāraṅg

• **Aparāhna (Noon):**

Sāraṅg	Surat̥sāraṅg	Jalsāraṅg
Bansīsāraṅg	Madmāvad	Gouḍsāraṅg
Bindrābansāraṅg	Naṭsāraṅg	

• **Sāyanha (Dusk):**

Naṭ	Prakīnaṭ	Maslānaṭ
Chayyānaṭ(Chāyānaṭ)	Mēghnaṭ	Bhīmpalās
Dhanāsarī	Pūrcī	Pūrbā
Pūrvī	Mārō	Gouḍ
Gaurī	Gaurā	

• **Pradōṣa (Evening):**

Siri	Jayatsiri	Mālvī
Mālsirī	Gauḍsirī	Siripant
Bhākā	Mōhankalyān	Kalyān
Śyāmkalyān	Amīrkalyān	Amīrnaṭ
Yamaṅkalyān	Yaman	Yamnī
Dīpak	Dīpakkalyān	Kāmūd
Jāmūd	Kāmūdkalyān	Jāmūdkalyān

Kōkabkalyān	Bhūpālī	Bhūpālīkalyān
Bhūpkalyān	Janjhōṭī	Mēghjanjhōṭī

- **Niṣitha (Night):**

Śankar	Kālangaḍā	Bahārānand
Kāpī	Mūlānīkāpī	Behāg
Śankarbēhāg	Dūdbacañbēhāg	Jajuvanti
Khamāj	Śudkhamāj	Nāyakī
Nāyakā	Pīlō	Paṭmanjarī
Kānaḍā	Jōgīkānaḍā	Būndīkānaḍā
Jiddīkānaḍā	Miyākānaḍā	Bākēsīrīkānaḍā
Bāgēsvar	Darbār	Rāṣṣā
Ṣahnā	Āḍhānā	Kēdhār

- **Triyamā (Midnight):**

Dēvgāndhār	Dēvugirī	Kōjarī	
Rāmkalī	Gunkalī	Pulkalī	
Bhairō	Prītambhairō	Bēbās	
Bhūpāl	Bohar	Vēsāk	Dēvagiri

Apart from these the author has also listed the raga-s that are sung during cloudy environments.

Mēgh	Malhār	Mēghmalhār
Surat	Suratmalhār	Dēsalmhār
Sāvan	Naṭṣāvan	

This is how the rāga-s are followed according to the time in hindustānī as dicussed in Sabhārañjani

1.7.3 Names of the Seven svāra-s:

The svāra-s in Hindusthāni system are indicated as Karaz(s), Rigap(r), Gandhār(g), Maddham(m), Pañcam(p), Dhaivat(d), Niṣād(n). Instead of ṣaḍja and ṛṣabha the author has used the terms karaz and rigap.

In India there are certain languages such as Avadh, Bhojpuri, Bengali, Braj and so on where colloquially they use ‘ra’ instead of ‘ḍa’, ‘ka’, ‘ga’ instead of ‘ṣa’.

So, it is to be noted that the author would have used these terms based on the interaction with the musicians from these regions certainly.

1.8 Observations:

- The introduction of the text states that the author is inspired by Bharata muni’s Nāṭya śāstra as a source and has written the work Sabhārañjani.
- As there were very few selected texts in Telugu, the author would have felt the need for the same and as a result, he must have compiled and documented this work.
- The author has slightly modified the names of two mēḷākarta-s Hēmavantinī and Sucāritrī. Probably these mēḷa-s were referred to in the same way during his times.
- The author has clearly mentioned in the preface of the text that the chapter on Hindustanī rāga-s has been written, after a series of interactions with the musicians who came from northern part of India and settled in southern part.
- So probably the author would have used the conversational terms karaz and rigap instead of ṣaḍja and ṛṣabha.

- Some of the names of the rāga-s differ in the names. The author has designated rāga Brindāvanisāraṅg as Bindrābansāraṅg, Chāyānaṭ as Chayyānaṭ colloquially. The author has used the same names that were in practice during his period.
- Therefore, it is very evident that the author had good knowledge on both Karṇāṭaka and Hindustānī traditions. He has equally patronized both the traditions in his court.
- The author has documented many of the concepts pertaining to Music and Dance that have been in practice from time immemorial and has carried forward the same to the posterity.

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